

Supplementary materials to

Creating coherent cycling networks: A spatial network science perspective

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Preliminary version

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Abbreviations

Betweenness centrality variants

- **SBC**: spatial betweenness centrality
- **PBC**: population-weighted betweenness centrality (same logic as sbc, but using population as weight instead of spatial coverage)
- **EBC**: standard edge betweenness centrality
- **FEBC**: based on ebc, but filtered to nodes with non-zero spatial weight (which is used to compute sbc)

Routing: Path types

- **SP**: shortest path (minimizing trip distance; routing cost equals segment length)
- **BP**: bikeable path (minimizing perceived trip distance; routing cost is computed from segment length and segment bikeability - see paper for details)

Distance cutoff and decay

Distance decay and cutoff always refer to trip distance (sum of segment length; for both SP and BP)

- **c2000**: 2 km cutoff
- **c4000**: 4 km cutoff
- **c7000**: 7 km cutoff
- **dec_2000_4000**: linear decay; 100% up to 2 km, linear decrease to 0% for 4 km
- **dec_4000_7000**: linear decay; 100% up to 4 km, linear decrease to 0% for 7 km
- **dec_2000_7000**: linear decay; 100% up to 2 km, linear decrease to 0% for 7 km

Result files

By default, each GeoPackage file uses the local UTM zone as spatial reference system (as generated by NetAScore).

Centrality

- GeoPackage of network edges (output of NetAScore) with additional columns containing the centrality results.
- file name: r_<case_id>_edges.gpkg

Priority Scores

- GeoPackage based on centrality results (centrality columns filtered) with priority score variants as additional edges
- file name: ps_<case_id>.gpkg

Summary statistics

- ps_stats.csv: priority score statistics.
h0/h1/h2: filtered to segments greater or equal to 1: 20% of max. PS; 2: 10% of max. PS; 3: 99th percentile of PS
b: bikeability
- remaining CSV files: results of centrality result comparisons (for node subsampling, distance cutoff or decay, and network simplification); share the same table structure (p: HC segment filter based on % of maximum centrality; q: HC segment filter based on quantile) - see code documentation for details

Columns

- Column names with suffix „_ft“ refer to forward direction and „_tf“ for backward direction (from-to / to-from nodes).
- index_bike_incwalk: bikeability index (also for segments which are not accessible by bike, but open for pedestrians)
- access_bicycle: Boolean value, indicating legal access
- centr_*: centrality result (see abbreviations list for name encoding)
e.g. *centr_sbc_c4000_bp_d4* for spatial betweenness centrality considering bikeable routes with routing factor of 4 and routing cutoff of 4 km
- ps_*: priority score result (name contains mode and centrality the priority score is based on); suffix: p1, p2, p3 referring to priority score variant and t (e.g. t0.8) referring to t-value or bikeability threshold (see paper)

SBC Distance variants

SBC Distance variants

SBC Distance variants

Distance comparison

Distance comparison

Centrality variants

Centrality variants

Centrality variants

Subsampling Distance

Priority Score variants

Wien

2 km

4 km

7 km

Importance

P0 / P1 t1.0

P1 t0.8

P2 t0.8

P3 t0.8

Priority Score variants

ZS

2 km

4 km

7 km

Importance

P0 / P1 t1.0

P1 t0.8

P2 t0.8

P3 t0.8

Priority Score variants

Priority Score variants

ZW 2 km 4 km 7 km

Importance

P0 / P1 t1.0

P1 t0.8

P2 t0.8

P3 t0.8

Priority Score variants

IB

2 km

4 km

7 km

Importance

P0 / P1 t1.0

P1 t0.8

P2 t0.8

P3 t0.8

Priority Score variants

NO 2 km 4 km 7 km

Importance

P0 / P1 t1.0

P1 t0.8

P2 t0.8

P3 t0.8

Network Simplification

Network Simplification

